

MPSD Research Data Policy

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DOI 10.5281/zenodo.15233732

9 July 2024

Executive summary

- MPSD publications should generally be available as open access (either through paid open access, or through upload to an e-print server such as arxiv.org).
- Research data associated with each publication should be published or archived at the time of publication of the manuscript (or earlier).

We follow “*as open as possible, as closed as necessary*”: unless there are pressing reasons not to, research data needs to be published (not just archived) with the associated publication.

- The responsibility for the research data for each publication is with all co-authors for their respective contributions.
- Reasonable exceptions can be granted by the directorate.

1 Why do research data matter?

Reproducibility is a core principle of science. Scientific results have to be reproducible [1]. To make them reproducible, it is essential that relevant research data sets, including software, are accessible to those who want to reproduce the work. Other good reasons to make our work reproducible include:

- (Growing) demands from publishers that submitted work must be reproducible (and associated reputational damage if publications are found not to be reproducible).
- Making results fully and easily reproducible helps new staff and students to continue the work started by others. This can save months of precious research time in our research groups.
- Requirements from research funding bodies and employers.

2 What are research data?

Research data associated with our scientific work include:

- Primary data from experiments and simulations.
- Reduced/secondary data from post-processing.
- Software, dependencies and installation instructions.
- Metadata, workflows and documentation (experimental conditions, what to install/execute/... in which order).

3 MPSD research data policy: publish data with publications

It is *MPSD's research data policy* that connected with every publication the relevant research data (including software and documentation) must be published or archived. This needs to be completed at the time of publication or before.

We follow the principle of *as open as possible, as closed as necessary*: the initial assumption is that research data associated with a publication will be published. See Fig. 1 on the following page, and section below for example.

Where research data sets cannot be *published*, they must instead be *archived*, so that the archive can be retrieved and given to parties who want to reproduce the published study. Reasons that may prevent research data publication include contractual agreements with research partners, ethical concerns, pending patent applications etc. If you think you cannot publish your data, you need to get agreement from your supervisor.

The Digital Object Identifier (DOI) of the research data publication or of the research data archive should be cited in the manuscript.

Figure 1: *Publication process flowchart with publication and archival of research data.*

4 Research data publication example

1. Gather relevant research data in directory structure (see section 5).
2. Upload research data to a research data repository (for example “Zenodo” or “Edmond” [3]). The repository will provide a Digital Object Identifier (DOI) for that data set.
3. Cite that DOI in the publication manuscript.

See Figure 1 and [2] for more details.

5 What data do we need to keep?

Broadly speaking we need to keep all the data necessary to reproduce the main results in the publication. Of particular importance are primary data that are hard to re-create: perhaps an experiment is difficult to repeat, or a simulation was so time-demanding that it is not practical to repeat. For simulation-based science, we must keep all configuration files, software specifications, workflows, etc. so that the simulation can (at least in principle) be repeated.

However, some data sets may be too large to publish in their entirety. There is no generic rule; if in doubt, please agree an acceptable solution with your supervisor. See [2] for a more detailed discussion and guidance. The research data management team¹ is available to provide advice.

6 Research data not related to publications

There may be data sets that need to be kept and which are not directly associated with a publication, such as a PhD thesis, or a research project. These can be published (e.g. [3] or Zenodo) or archived (e.g. [4], [5]) in the same way as data sets associated with publications.

7 Data on computing resources

Data on computing services (such as home directories in laptops/desktops, network drives, home and scratch in high performance computing installations, other storage locations) will be deleted when the associated computing account expires (typically when the student/staff leaves the Institute). The researcher needs to publish (e.g. [3] or Zenodo) or archive (e.g. [4], [5]) any data of scientific importance prior to the account expiration.

8 Responsibilities

It is the responsibility of each scientist (including PhD students) to make their publications reproducible and thus take care of the publication/archiving of the associated research data. Co-authors of a multi-author publication carry joint responsibility for the reproducibility of their respective contributions, and the corresponding author is responsible for the coordination.

The preparation of the research data for publication can be a substantial effort and is an important contribution to a publication.

9 Further reading

- [1] MPG's Rules of conduct for good scientific practice (<https://www.mpg.de/197494/rulesScientificPractice.pdf>) and MPSD's summary on research data management (<https://www.mpsd.mpg.de/893042.pdf>)
- [2] Guidance for reproducible publications: <https://cs.mpsd.mpg.de/docs/reproducibility.html>
- [3] Edmond: MPG service for research data publication: <https://cs.mpsd.mpg.de/docs/edmond.html>
- [4] Keeper: MGP service for research data archival: <https://cs.mpsd.mpg.de/docs/keeper.html>
- [5] General notes on archiving research data: <https://cs.mpsd.mpg.de/docs/archive.html>

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